

VETERINARY SCIENCES

INVESTIGATION OF THE PROPERTIES OF MYCOBACTERIAL CULTURES ISOLATED FROM BOVINE BLOOD

Yuliia Andriienko

Junior Research Fellow

Anatoliy Paliy

doctor of veterinary sciences, professor

Mykola Bogach

doctor of veterinary sciences, professor

National Scientific Center «Institute of Experimental and

Clinical Veterinary Medicine»,

83, Grigory Skovorody St., Kharkiv, 61023, Ukraine

Abstract

The species affiliation of mycobacterial cultures isolated from the blood of cattle, as well as reference strains of mycobacteria belonging to Runyon groups II, III, and IV, was determined. The cultural and biochemical properties of the mycobacteria were studied. It was established that the hemocultures of mycobacteria belong to the species *Mycobacterium avium* and exhibit pathogenic properties in rabbits and chickens.

Keywords: mycobacteria, cultural and biochemical properties, laboratory animals, virulence

Introduction

Tuberculosis in farm animals remains a significant issue for livestock production in many countries worldwide [1, 2]. Specific prevention of this disease is not available, as vaccination against tuberculosis is currently not permitted under European Union legislation, due to its interference with diagnostic procedures in eradication programs based on intradermal testing [3].

The main method for ante-mortem diagnosis of tuberculosis is the intradermal tuberculin test using highly specific allergens [4, 5]. However, during routine allergic testing, cases of non-specific reactions in animals to the administration of PPD-tuberculin for mammals have been reported [6, 7].

The nature of these reactions is diverse, but the primary cause is considered to be the sensitization of animals by atypical mycobacteria [8, 9].

Atypical mycobacteria are ubiquitous and exhibit exceptional resistance to adverse environmental factors [10, 11].

Ensuring tuberculosis-free status and effective control of the disease require the development of new diagnostic and preventive methods, which is not possible without analyzing the current epizootic situation [12].

The isolation and identification of mycobacteria as etiological agents of animal tuberculosis and para-allergic reactions to the administration of PPD-tuberculin for mammals remain highly relevant tasks today.

Materials and methods. During the study, 13 mycobacterial cultures were used (6 reference and 7 field isolates (*M. avium*)), including 8 strains of *Mycobacterium avium* and 5 strains of atypical mycobacteria belonging to Runyon groups II (*M. scrofulaceum*), III (*M. intracellulare*), and IV (*M. fortuitum*, *M. phlei*, *M. smegmatis*) according to the Runyon classification (1959).

The experimental mycobacterial cultures were cultivated on solid Helberg nutrient medium. Species identification of mycobacteria was performed using biochemical tests (Tween 80 hydrolysis, amidase activity—nicotinamidase, pyrazinamidase, urease—catalase activity, and tellurite reduction) and cultural characteristics (growth rate, ability to grow at 22.0 °C, 42.0 °C and 45.0 °C, and tolerance to 5.0 % NaCl in the medium).

The studies were conducted in accordance with the *Guidelines for the Identification of Mycobacterial Cultures* (Kharkiv, 2015).

Biological studies were conducted in accordance with current regulatory documents using laboratory animals (rabbits, chickens, and guinea pigs). All manipulations were performed under conditions aimed at minimizing stress and suffering of the animals. The study was conducted in accordance with the European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrate Animals used for Experimental and Other Scientific Purposes [13].

Research results. In order to determine or confirm the species identity of mycobacterial cultures isolated from cattle blood, as well as reference cultures, their cultural (growth rate, colony morphology, photochromogenicity, and growth at 25.0°C, 37.0°C, and 45.0°C) and biochemical properties (tolerance to 5.0% NaCl, accumulation of citrate-ammonium iron, catalase activity, reaction with potassium tellurite, Tween 80, and amides) were studied.

Based on the results of studying the cultural and biochemical properties of mycobacterial cultures (Table 1), it was established that all 7 cultures (Nos. 2–8) isolated from cattle blood (hemocultures), as well as 6 reference (control) cultures (Nos. 1, 9–13), exhibited characteristic cultural and biochemical features typical of the respective mycobacterial species belonging to Runyon groups II, III, and IV.

Table 1.

Study of the Cultural and Biochemical Properties of Mycobacteria Isolated from the Blood of Cattle

No.	Mycobacterial cultures	Primary growth, days	Growth at temperature			Pigment production	Iron accumulation	Tolerance to 5% NaCl	Catalase activity	Reaction with potassium tellurite	Tween 80 hydrolysis	Amidase activity	
			25.0 °C	37.0 °C	45.0 °C							Nicotinamide	Pyrazinamide
1	<i>M. avium</i> № 61	17.0±2.4	+	+	+	N	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
2	<i>M. avium</i> 8/07	4.0±0.6	+	+	+	N	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
3	<i>M. avium</i> 9/07	3.0±0.5	+	+	+	N	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
4	<i>M. avium</i> 15/07	18.0±2.9	+	+	+	C	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
5	<i>M. avium</i> 22/07	4.0±0.3	+	+	+	N	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
6	<i>M. avium</i> 36/07	5.0±0.8	+	+	+	N	+	-	-	+	+	+	+
7	<i>M. avium</i> 63/07	20.0±3.1	+	+	+	N	+	-	-	+	+	+	+
8	<i>M. avium</i> 64/07	19.0±3.3	+	+	+	C	-	-	+	+	+	+	+
9	<i>M. scrofulaceum</i>	15.0±2.7	+	+	+	N	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
10	<i>M. intracellu- laræ</i>	15.0±2.3	+	+	+	C	+	-	-	-	+	+	+
11	<i>M. smegmatis</i>	3.0±0.7	+	+	+	N	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
12	<i>M. fortuitum</i>	7.0±1.6	+	+	+	N	-	+	-	+	+	+	+
13	<i>M. phlei</i>	8.0±1.2	+	+	+	N	-	+	-	+	+	+	+

Notes: “+” – positive reaction; “-” – negative reaction; N – no pigment; C – pigment present

To study the pathogenic and virulent properties of the experimental hemocultures of mycobacteria, a biological assay was performed on susceptible laboratory animals. A total of 26 guinea pigs, 10 rabbits, and 10 chickens were selected for the study. The selected animals were clinically healthy and aged 3–4 months.

Prior to the experiment, the animals were subjected to an allergic test in accordance with the current Guidelines for the Use of Tuberculins for the Allergic Diagnosis of Tuberculosis in Mammals and Birds (1994).

The reactions in guinea pigs and rabbits were recorded at 24 and 48 hours, respectively, and in chickens at 30–36 hours. In all selected animals, allergic reactions to PPD-tuberculin for mammals and birds, as well as to atypical mycobacteria antigen (AAM), were negative.

Subsequently, the animals were inoculated with a suspension of mycobacterial cultures at a concentration of 1.0 mg of bacterial mass per 1.0 cm³ of sterile isotonic solution, administered at a dose of 1.0 cm³ per animal. Rabbits and chickens were inoculated with suspensions of *M. avium* cultures only, while guinea pigs received a mixture of all experimental hemocultures.

The laboratory animals were observed for 90 days. Allergic testing was performed periodically, once every 30 days, and in the event of animal death, pathological material was collected for bacteriological examination for tuberculosis.

It was established that all experimental mycobacterial cultures caused enlargement of regional lymph nodes in guinea pigs. During the study period, transient

positive reactions to allergen administration were observed. At the site of inoculation of the mycobacterial suspension, guinea pigs exhibited hyperemia and swelling up to 4 mm in diameter, while chickens showed thickening and hyperemia of the wattles.

The study of the virulent properties of *M. avium* in rabbits and chickens demonstrated its virulent activity. The results of biochemical studies for species identification of the cultures were also confirmed.

The experimental mycobacterial cultures exhibited pronounced virulent effects in laboratory animals. In rabbits, signs of cachexia gradually developed following infection. By day 23 post-inoculation, six rabbits infected with *M. avium* cultures (reference strain, No. 63/07, and No. 64/07) had died.

Post-mortem examination of the dead rabbits revealed hepatosplenomegaly, generalized emaciation, and enlargement of lymph nodes, indicating a septic form of the disease (Yersin type). Rabbits infected with culture No. 15/07 died on day 33 of the experiment. Pathological examination showed a similar pattern (sepsis) as in the previous animals, along with joint swelling and the presence of seropurulent fluid in the synovial sacs. During necropsy, pathological material from all rabbits was collected for bacteriological examination.

A rabbit infected with *M. intracellulare* died on day 60 post-inoculation. However, no characteristic tuberculous lesions were observed at necropsy, and tissue samples (liver, spleen, lungs) were collected for further bacteriological analysis.

Mortality in chickens was observed starting from day 46 of the experiment. Chickens infected with *M.*

avium (reference strain) and culture No. 64/07 died on day 46, exhibiting characteristic signs of emaciation, weight loss, feather loss, and swollen, hyperemic wattles.

At necropsy, enlargement of the liver and spleen was noted, with characteristic white-gray nodules on the surface and within the parenchyma of these organs. The spleen was enlarged, edematous, and had a purple-red coloration. Chickens that died on day 48 of the experiment showed similar clinical signs and pathological changes at necropsy.

Guinea pigs infected with the experimental cultures did not die during the course of the experiment. After 90 days, the guinea pigs were euthanized, and biological material was collected for bacteriological examination. At necropsy, no pathological changes characteristic of tuberculosis were observed, except for enlargement of regional lymph nodes.

During bacteriological examination of pathological material collected from all experimental laboratory animals, the original mycobacterial cultures were re-isolated.

Thus, the conducted studies made it possible to determine the species identity of the isolated mycobacterial hemocultures and to investigate their cultural, morphological, sensitizing, pathogenic, and virulent properties.

Conclusion

1. Mycobacterial cultures isolated from the blood of cattle that showed a positive reaction to the intradermal administration of PPD-tuberculin for mammals belong to the *Mycobacterium avium-intracellulare* complex. Based on cultural and biochemical characteristics, seven of the isolated mycobacterial cultures were identified as *Mycobacterium avium*.

2. Mycobacteria of the *Mycobacterium avium-intracellulare* complex are pathogenic for rabbits and chickens.

3. Atypical mycobacteria of Runyon groups II, III, and IV induce sensitization to PPD-tuberculin for mammals in guinea pigs and are non-pathogenic for this species of laboratory animals.

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